

**TRADITIONAL AND MODERN APPROACHES TO DETERMINATION,
EVALUATION, AND MONITORING OF SOIL DEGRADATION**

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Measures to protect soils from degradation processes will be of great importance in increasing the efficiency of agricultural lands in the future. In carrying out this task, special attention is paid to the rational use of land resources, identification, assessment, and mapping of such lands to plan and implement measures to protect soils.

When planning different methods of soil protection, it is first necessary to identify the areas where measures are required to protect them and to assess the level of risk that the degradation process may occur in these areas.

Soil degradation is a process of changing soil formation processes and permanent deterioration of soil properties as a result of human activities, which in extreme cases can lead to the destruction of the biosphere and desertification of areas.

The regularity of the formation of degradation processes depends on various indicators found, in particular, on the state of the natural environment in remote sensing materials. Indicators are easily observed components of the physiognomic parts of landscapes - relief, vegetation, hydrographic networks, etc., or a combination of them manifested as the morphological composition of natural-territorial complexes at different levels.

More than 1 billion hectares of land on almost all continents around the world have been degraded. The causes and main factors of degradation processes are different. It is known that the combination of several factors leads to degradation, the combined effect of which dramatically worsens the environmental situation.

In areas prone to degradation, the physical properties of the soil deteriorate, loss of vegetation, salinization of groundwater, biological productivity decreases sharply, and as a result, the chances of ecosystem regeneration decrease.

Soil degradation is a complex and diverse set of processes associated with a decrease in moisture content over large areas and a decrease in the biological productivity of soil-plant ecosystems. In many parts of the world, lands bordering desert areas are degraded due to unfavorable conditions, leading to the loss of thousands of hectares of land per year. It also accelerates this process by ruthlessly exploiting large areas through the irrational use of ordinary farming, pastures, and other agricultural lands, planting without crop rotation or leaving the soil unattended. Detection and assessment of soil degradation, development of measures to prevent it is one of the most pressing issues today. Extensive experience has been accumulated in recording, combating, assessing, classifying, and mapping the risk of degradation processes.

Many scientists who have studied the processes of degradation in soils believe that soil salinity is one of the main indicators of this process. Therefore, the study of soil salinity is the basis for determining the causes of degradation processes.

In the fight against soil salinity, it is recommended to establish drainage and, in particular, alfalfa planting as a measure to reduce evaporation of moisture from the soil surface [1].

The application of aerospace methods in soil science has significantly contributed to the development of soil mapping and soil cover observation. In the 1930s, from the earliest days of the use of aerosols for the study of natural resources, it was discovered that there were significant possibilities for the use of remote imaging in compiling detailed soil maps and assessing crop status.

Remote methods of studying soil cover - allow reflecting different levels of origin of secondary changes in the soil. Each soil type has its spectral-brightness image in space images. By using different methods of processing aerospace images, it is possible to identify different soils and their specific properties.

Remote soil surveys often reveal the possibility of identifying saline and brackish soils. This is often the case for areas with natural salinity (arid lands), as well as areas with local salinization caused by irrigation measures. Salinization leads to abrupt changes in soil properties and causes thinning or disappearance of vegetation cover [2].

Primarily, this applies to saline soils. Sodium-saturated soil colloids undergo peptization, soil aggregates break down, and the physical properties of the soil change. The maximum change in soil density, aggregate, and mechanical composition is observed. From what has been said above, it is clear that secondary salinity radically alters the various properties of soils, resulting in the spectral-brightness image of saline and brackish soils in space images being distinctive.

The first ideas about the possibility of assessing the salinization process of irrigated soils based on remote data began in the 60s of the 20th century, but such data were very rare at that time. Subsequent studies in arid, mainly cotton-growing areas, provided more detailed data, which then provided insights into what data on soil salinity could be obtained from the images and what were the signs of decoding the salinity of different types of soils.

When creating large-scale maps of soil types and types, it is necessary to determine the process of salinization and salinization. It turns out that in aero- and space photography, such soil types look good in changing the color and appearance of the image. According to Yu.P.Kienko and Yu.K.Kelner, 10 m near-space images provide 100% information about the forms of elementary soil structures, and in the 20th 30 m space images allow to identify no more than 80% of the data [3].

The process of practical decoding of spatial images involves working with a series of images. It is recommended to work with images of the same area in different brightness, depending on the characteristics, condition, and shooting parameters of the objects and conditions.

The most commonly used are: images in different spectral ranges, multi-zone images propagating along the wavelength, images at different times, images in different lighting conditions, images in different directions, images of different sizes. One of the effective methodological methods is the sequential interpretation used when different objects are displayed in different zonal images. For example, soils that differ in salinity and salinity levels are best seen in the blue zones in the images, while swampy soils and soils that differ in moisture levels are seen in areas close to the infrared zones in the image.

Serial decoding work involves the analysis of fragments of spatial images obtained over some time with the creation of the decoding.

Determination of saline soils is one of the most important tasks in the process of remote soil reclamation. When observing the salt regime of irrigated soils, the degree and type of soil salinity, the direction of change of rock salinity, salt reserves, and causes of salinization are assessed.

Maps of saline lands of Uzbekistan were made by compiling a small-scale soil map [4]. While working on the mapping, black and white images of different sizes were used. The spotted and fine-spotted structure of the photograph, from light gray to dark gray, is marked for the salts.

Tadjiev U.T. developed a special map of soil salinity by Spatial images also show small spots of low and moderately saline soils scattered between unsalted gray-grass soils, which are depicted in images as light-gray and gray photons in which the boundaries are not clearly defined.

VL Andronikov recorded detailed data on soil salinity by decoding black-and-white images obtained during the seasons [6].

Deciphering the salinity of irrigated soils in arid areas is carried out according to the condition of the cotton crop planted in the fields [7]. Under these conditions, it is not possible to decipher the surface of the open soil, because the coefficients of spectral brightness of non-saline arid soils and saline soils are very close to each other.

Tone and image are some of the main deciphering signs of salinity. Two sharply different tones were adopted: dark - for plots with good condition of cotton, and light tone - for plots with no or very little cotton plant. Based on the field observations of the soil, the proportion of light-colored spots within the field or contour and their size provide an opportunity to statistically substantiate that the image is related to the salinity level in the 1.0-meter layer of soil.

This principle made it possible to distinguish four soil gradations in large-scale images, three in medium-sized images, and two in spatial images during visual observation.

In the 80s and 90s of the twentieth century, the decipherment of soil complexes from space images was carried out mainly using the method of structural-zonal analysis. Today, satellites are equipped with high-resolution optical surveillance equipment that allows them to capture images in digital form. In this regard, instead of optical sequential spectral analysis, other methods of processing the original digital data are being used.

Among the new methods of remote data processing, the Data Fusion Technology method has a special place and is a method of data entry and integration. The essence of data aggregation is to use complex approaches in obtaining, processing, and interpreting spatial information.

Data Fusion Technology uses different time images from different ranges of the electromagnetic spectrum, summarizes the different processing results of the initial data, uses data obtained from different experiments, the results of surface research, special cartographic materials, and more. The method of data aggregation is applied when the state of the system under study using the remote study of objects is changing. Data on soil salinity fall into this category.

Among the most effective methods of estimating saline soils using modern methods are methods such as spectral division, maximum closeness to reality, classification based on uncertain groups, comparison of intervals, analysis of key components, correlation equations. Modeling and forecasting of temporal and spatial variability of salinity are carried out using integrated methods of data aggregation and separation.

In 1998-1999, large-scale experiments using remote methods to map soil salinity were conducted in the Canadian province of Alberta. As part of this work, two key areas were studied, one of which was naturally saline, and the other - areas that were saline as a result of artificial irrigation.

layer from 0 to the depth was studied using an electromagnetic inductometer device. 60 cm Remote studies were performed using a multispectral sensor mounted on the aircraft. In the first year of the study, images were obtained at 3 4 M, and in the second year at 0,5 M resolution.

Four ranges of electromagnetic waves were used: blue (0.45-0.52 mm), green (0.52-0.60 mm), red, and similar elements were used in the Data Fusion Technology method. GIMetternicht [8-9-10-11-12-13] has considered the use of many fuzzy methods to increase the efficiency of saline soil segregation based on remote data.

He studied Landsat TM-type space images taken over saline areas in Bolivia. Modeling of saline areas using many fuzzy methods allowed to increase the accuracy of the results. Up to 44% accuracy was achieved in the separation of chloride-sulfate-type saline soils. High accuracy was obtained in the separation of sulfate-chloride salts and saline soils, while the data of the near and thermal infrared channels of the spectrum provided the best reliable information.

In conclusion, the application of space imagery processing research through modern GAT technologies can open up new directions in the study of soil salinization and degradation processes. As we can see, the direction of this research is being carried out in many countries, regardless of whether or not they own satellites to earth.

Spatial imaging of Landsat satellites is the most widely used for research, the advantage of which is a large number of research channels, convenience, high accuracy, and the availability of corrective actions. Particular attention is paid to remote monitoring of soil salinity, especially in countries with arid climates (Australia, India, Turkey, southern Russia, etc.). Remote methods in assessing and mapping natural, anthropogenic salinization of soils and their consequent degradation processes in these areas have always yielded clear scientific results.

Such maps are developed based on processing GAT technologies of medium and high-resolution space images from Earth satellites Landsat, Spot, Ikonos, QuickBird, which is a great practical help in solving problems of assessing soil degradation processes.

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